

Guidelines for a Short Overview of a Basic Service at the End of the Initialisation Phase

Version 2, April 2026

The latest achievements of each Basic Service are regularly described in the Base4NFDI newsletters. However, at the end of the initialisation phase, a short overview of the service and the results of the initialisation phase should be written by the service teams as part of their Deliverable D.Ini.6. This short overview can be used as an abstract to be included as the first page of the final report of the initialisation phase.

Overview:

- **Length:** One page
- **Language:** English
- **Publication:** News item on the [Base4NFDI website](#) - will be mentioned, but not included, in the newsletter.
- **Target group:** Interested public – all visitors of the [Base4NFDI website](#) – NFDI consortia, TEC and International Advisory Board
- **Readability:** easily digestible
- **Deadline:** Preferably 3 days before the publication of the first Base4NFDI newsletter after the end of the initialisation phase, but no later than 6 weeks after the end of the initialisation phase.

The text should include a brief overview of the service:

- What can the service be used for?
- Who can use it?
- How can it be used?

This may include links to the service's website or to other documents such as the service's factsheet, but should provide enough information for the reader to understand the nature and purpose of the service without having to go to the service's website.

There should also be some information about the initialisation phase itself:

- What were the main achievements of the initialisation phase? (1-2 sentences)
- What are the important results of the initialisation phase, i.e. its deliverables (see [Wittenhorst, T. et al. \(2026\)](#): Requirements analysis, software evaluation, service design, service prototype, service piloting and user testing)?
- What were the highlights (e.g. workshops, publications, etc.) of the initialisation phase?

Finally, there should be a short (1-2 sentences) outlook on the integration phase (if applicable).